

Rice Yellow Mottle Virus (RYMV) Nursery were observed to be B1 resistant. This is because most of the lines developed for RYMV resistance came from adapted upland varieties, such as 63-83, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan, which are also B1 resistant.

Cluster analysis of the results by groups of entries from the same origin showed that African and Latin American entries performed at par or better than those from Asia, USA, Europe, and the Middle East with respect to proportion of B1-resistant entries (see figure, b). Of the entries with superior performance, more originated from Africa than from Latin America.

The close similarity in superior performance of improved African and Latin American entries reflects the similarities in the host-pathogen-stress complex. Some traditional varieties have been used more often than others in the parentage of the B1-tolerant lines

Blast scores for 1,253 entries in 1991 INGER-Africa nurseries grouped into major ecosystems or stresses and by region. Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 0-9.

originating from different regions (see table). These include varieties 63-83, Colombia 1, Dourado Precoce, Iguape Cateto, and Moroberekan.

The results indicate that adapted genotypes from Africa and Latin America serve as good sources for durable B1 resistance for upland rice in Africa. □

Reaction of some rice cultures to leaf blast (BI), brown spot (BS), and leaf scald (LSc)

M. Saifulla, B. M. Devaiah, and H. L. Vasanthakumar, Agricultural Research Station, Ponnampet 571216, S. Coorg, Karnataka, India

We screened rice cultures Kalinga, CR628-2, CR635-42, Karna, IET7 191, and Intan during the 1988 and 1989 wet seasons in fields with high disease

pressure. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Plot size was 6 × 3 m. We applied fertilizer 60-75-87.5 kg NPK/ha. Total rainfall during crop growth was 644.8 mm in 1988 and 1,389.3 mm in 1989.

All of the entries were moderately to highly susceptible to leaf BI, moderately susceptible to susceptible to BS, and susceptible to LSc (see table). Days to 50% flowering, plant height, and yield for each culture are reported in the table. □

Reaction of rice cultures to leaf BI, BS, and LSc.

Culture	Disease score ^a			Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
	Leaf blast	Brown spot	Leaf scald			
Kalinga	9	7	7	86	67.8	1.1
CR628-2	9	7	7	97	64.5	1.1
CR635-42	9	6	7	97	77.3	1.1
<i>Checks</i>						
Karna	9	7	7	90	62.1	2.0
IET7191	9	5	7	107	67.6	2.4
Intan	7	6	7	117	67.9	2.0
LSD (0.05)						0.1

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Grain quality

Aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu, India

S. Arurnugachamy, S. Vairavan, P. Vivekanandan, and S. Palanisumy, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TRRI), Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

Consumers in Tamil Nadu prefer rice Varieties with good cooking quality and scent. These rices receive a premium price in the market and have export potential. Many of them are tall indicas that lodge easily and have low yield potential. We evaluated 10 quality rice varieties of medium duration (around 140 d) during the 1990 thaladi season (Sep-Oct to Jan-Feb) to assess their

performance and feasibility of use as donors for aromatic and quality rice improvement in Tamil Nadu.

We transplanted 30-d-old seedlings in 10-m² plots with 20- × 10-cm spacing. We used 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

Milled rice samples were used to assess scent in a cooking test. It was evaluated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

The two glutinous rice varieties Black Puttu and White Puttu, both with tall plant stature, recorded 2.5 and 1.7 t/ha, respectively (see table). Both Jeeraga Samba types are characterized by low rough rice weight and moderate yield

potential. Dwarf-statured, nonlodging varieties IET8580 (Kasthuri) and IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1) have brown rice, length of more than 7 mm, and an L:B ratio of about 4. They possess good yield potential. IET8580 is strongly

scented; IET10364 is lightly scented.

The superiority of Pusa Basmati 1 was revealed in this study. It is being used as donor in the breeding program to improve aromatic and quality rice varieties in Tamil Nadu. □

Performance of quality rice varieties at TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pedigree	Duration (d)	Plant ht at maturity (cm)	Yield (t/ha)	1000-grain wt ^a (g)	Brown rice			Shape ^b	Scent ^c
						Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	L:B		
Black Puttu	Local	134	131	2.5	21.2	6.9	2.0	3.5	S	0
White Puttu	Local	144	134	1.7	23.8	7.0	2.5	2.8	M	0
AEB148	Jeeraga Samba-nonscented	140	137	1.5	10.2	4.5	2.2	2.0	B	0
AEB178	Jeeraga Samba-scented	140	140	1.7	10.0	4.4	2.2	2.0	B	2
Sugadas	Local	142	142	2.0	21.0	6.7	2.7	2.5	M	1
Rascadam	Local	135	145	1.1	11.4	4.3	2.3	1.9	B	1
HBC19	Karnal Local	141	109	0.8	20.8	7.7	1.8	4.3	S	1
Basmati 370	Local	141	110	1.8	21.5	7.5	1.9	3.9	S	1
IET8580 (Kasthuri)	Basmati 370/CR88-17-1-5	139	103	1.9	20.8	7.3	1.9	3.8	S	1
IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1)	Pusa 167/Karnal Local	134	88	2.4	18.4	7.4	1.8	4.1	S	2

^aRough rice basis. ^bS = slender, M = medium, B = bold. ^c0 = nonscented, 1 = lightly scented, 2 = scented. Based on SES.

Effect of plant density on rice grain quality

M. A. Karim, A. Ali, L. Ali, S. S. Ali, A. Mahmood, A. Majid, and T. A. Akhtar, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

We tested three levels of plant densities—118, 560, 160, 550, and 197,600 plants/ha—for Basmati 385 and advanced line 4048 during 1989-90 and 1990-91 cropping seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in 4- × 6-m plots. Data were averaged.

Thousand-grain weight, cooked grain length, total milling recovery, head rice recovery, and protein content decreased as plant densities of both varieties

increased (see table). The effect of plant density on kernel dimension, amylose content, and gel length was not consistent. □

Effect of plant density on grain quality parameters, 1989-90, 1990-91.^a

Quality character	Basmati 385			Basmati line 4048		
	118,560	160,550	197,600	118,560	160,550	197,600
Grain length (mm)	6.75 a	6.74 a	6.72 a	7.28 a	7.29 a	7.19 b
Grain width (mm)	1.63 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.62 a	1.60 a
1000-grain wt (g)	15.02 a	14.84 a	14.69 a	16.28 a	16.11 b	15.41 c
Cooked grain length (mm)	13.50 a	13.30 b	13.10 c	13.95 a	13.75 a	13.45 b
Total milled rice (%)	70.40 a	70.00 a	69.60 a	70.30 a	69.80 a	69.00 b
Head rice (%)	54.60 a	53.00 ab	51.43 b	52.70 a	50.90 b	48.00 c
Bursting of grains upon cooking (%)	6.50 a	8.33 a	9.17 a	4.50 a	4.60 a	5.50 a
Protein content (%)	9.10 a	8.70 a	8.40 a	8.90 a	8.60 a	8.40 a
Amylose content (%)	25.00 a	24.90 a	24.90 a	23.70 b	23.70 b	24.90 a
Gel length (mm)	67.50 b	65.60 b	84.50 a	66.50 b	65.10 b	79.00 a

^aValues in a row followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

Comparison of grain quality of mechanically and hand-harvested rice

A. Ali, M. A. Karim, A. Majid, L. Ali, S. S. Ali, and M. A. Khan, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Lahore, Punjab, Pakistan

Combine harvesters are becoming popular in Punjab, Pakistan, because of the shortage of farm labor during the peak harvest season.

From 15 locations in Sahiwal, Okara, and Kasur districts, we collected samples of KS282 (medium-grain) and Basmati

Grain quality of mechanically harvested and hand-harvested rice.^a

Character ^b	KS282		Basmati 198	
	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested
Moisture content (%)	29.7 a	20.2 b	30.5 a	21.0 b
Green and immature grains (%)	11.2 a	4.0 b	14.1 a	6.2 b
Production of husked grains (%)	2.1 a	0.0 b	3.2 a	0.0 b
Total milling recovery (% db)	69.8 b	71.5 a	68.7 b	70.0 a
Head rice recovery (% db)	54.2 b	58.1 a	50.0 b	55.0 a

^aIn a row, values followed by the same letter for each variety are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bdb = dry basis.

198 (fine-grain) that were harvested with a Ford New Holland model 8040 combine harvester. A small portion of

the same fields was harvested and grains threshed by hand for comparison. Results were averaged across locations.